

10. D. K. J. GORECKI and E. M. HAWES, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1977, 20, 124.
11. E. M. HAWES, D. K. J. GORECKI and D. D. JOHNSON, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1978, 16, 849.
12. E. M. HAWES and D. G. WIBBERLEY, *J. Chem. Soc. C*, 1967, 1564.
13. J. O. VINCENT and H. W. VINCENT, *Proc. Soc. Expt. Biol. Med.*, 1944, 55, 162.
14. S. SRIPTER, S. DAYTON, B. NOVIC and E. MUNTWYLER, *Arch. Biochem.*, 1950, 25, 191.
15. E. M. HAWES and D. G. WIBBERLEY, *J. Chem. Soc. C*, 1966, 315.

**Chemical Examination of the Leaves of
Juniperus bermudiana Linn.
(Cupressaceae)**

(Miss) F. KHATOON, IMDAD U. KHAN

and

W. H. ANSARI*

Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University,
Aligarh-202 001

Manuscript received 9 July 1984, revised 30 December 1985,
accepted 17 February 1986

JUNIPERUS bermudiana Linn. (Syn. *J. virginiana*) was examined only for its biflavonoid contents¹. We have undertaken a thorough investigation of *J. bermudiana* leaves. Dried and powdered leaves (1.5 kg) procured from F. R. I., Dehradun (India), were extracted exhaustively with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°), benzene, ethyl acetate and acetone. Petroleum ether and benzene extracts were combined and concentrated. The residue was chromatographed over Si-gel column affording the following compounds. Identification is based on spectral studies and also comparison of m.ps. and spectral data with those reported.

n-Hexane elution : It gave a white crystalline compound (150 mg), m.p. 63°, M^+ 408, analysed for $C_{29}H_{60}$; ν_{max} (KBr) 2 880 and 1 465 cm^{-1} ; m/e 408 (M^+), 379, 350, 336, 322, 308, 297 and 157; τ (CCl_4) 8.75 (60H, s); confirmed its identity as nonacosane (lit.² m.p. 63.6-64°).

Further elution with the same solvent provided an another crystalline compound (80 mg), m.p. 84°, M^+ 429, $C_{29}H_{60}O$; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 300 (OH), 2 890, 1 460, 1 370, 1 330, 1 120, 1 080, 1 055, 850 and 710 cm^{-1} ; m/e 424 (M^+), 409 ($M-CH_3$), 406 ($M-H_2O$), 378 ($M-H_2O-C_2H_4$) and 297 ($M-C_9H_{19}$), and peaks of masses separated by 14 units (CH_2) with increasing intensity (characteristics of long chain alcohol); τ (CCl_4) 8.75 (59H, s) and 7.55 (1H, s); suggested it to be 1-nonacosanol (lit.³ m.p. 84-5°); further confirmed by acetylation with Ac_2O-Py , τ (CCl_4) 8.75 (59H, s) and 8.35 (3H, s, 1-OAc).

Petrol benzene (7 : 3) elution : It afforded a LB positive white solid which on crystallisation (petrol-ether) yielded needles (70 mg), m.p. 165° (lit. m.p.

167°); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 350, 1 720, 1 690, 1 658, 1 640, 1 004, 914, 880, 830 cm^{-1} ; τ ($CDCl_3$) 9.01 (3H, s), 8.94 (3H, s), 8.78 (3H, s), 5.23, 5.00, 4.68 and 4.13 (m). Spectral data were found identical in all respects with those reported for sandaracopimeric acid^{4,5}.

Ethyl acetate extract : On further purification by solvent treatment and column chromatography followed by preparative tlc yielded three biflavonoids labelled as JBI, JBII and JBIII. Each was analysed separately by methylation and acetylation followed by pmr determination and found identical in m.p., chromatographic and spectral data with the reported biflavonoids¹.

Acetone extract : The brown residue on purification by paper chromatography (n-BuOH-AcOH- H_2O , 4 : 1 : 5) yielded a yellow compound, m.p. 181°, R_f 0.80. On hydrolysis (10% HCl), it gave an aglycone, m.p. 315°, identified as quercetin by comparing R_f , m.p. and shade in uv light of its methyl ether⁷, and a sugar. The sugar was confirmed as rhamnose by pc (n-BuOH-AcOH- H_2O , 4 : 1 : 5, R_f 0.31); n-BuOH- $EtOH-H_2O$, 4 : 1 : 2, R_f 0.36; yellow brown colour with aniline hydrogen phthalate as spraying reagent. The glycosidic linkage was established by methylation ($Me_2SO_4-K_2CO_3$) followed by acid hydrolysis. The partial methyl ether, m.p. 195° obtained, was acetylated (Ac_2O-Py) to give an acetate, m.p. 159°. Pmr spectrum showed the oxygenation pattern of quercetin with one acetoxy at τ 7.71 and four methoxyls at τ 6.18-6.23. Mass spectrum of the partial methyl ether provided main peaks at m/e 358 (M^+ , 100%), 343 ($M-CH_3$), 329 ($M-HCO$), 180 and 179 (RDA fragments). The fragments m/e 329 and 179 confirmed OH group at C-3. Bathochromic shift⁸ of 55 nm (in band I) with $AlCl_3$ further confirmed OH at C-3. The glycosidation was therefore at C-3. The structure of the compound was thus assigned as quercetin-3-O-rhamnoside⁹. This is the first report of the occurrence of these compounds in the family Cupressaceae.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (I.U.K.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

1. S. K. ROY, M. A. QASIM, M. KAMIL, M. ILYAS and W. RAHMAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, 61, 172.
2. I. HEILBRON and H. M. BUNBURY, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", Oxford University Press, 1958, Vol. III, p. 820.
3. C. D. HODGMAN, "A Hand Book of Chemistry and Physics", Chemical Rubber Publishing, U. S. A., 1960, p. 1123.
4. K. A. ZIRVI, K. JEWERS and M. J. NAGLER, *Planta Med.*, 1977, 32, 244.
5. L. J. GOUGH and J. S. MILLS, *Phytochemistry*, 1970, 9, 1093.
6. O. E. EDWARDS, A. NICOLSON and M. N. RODGER, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1960, 38, 663.

NOTES

7. T. A. GRISMAN, "The Chemistry of Flavonoid Compounds", Pergamon Press, New York, 1962, p. 423.
8. Ref. 7, p. 122.
9. Ref. 7, p. 337.

and Kashmir State. The local inhabitants in this high altitude desert consume the seeds of this plant as a dietary item. General composition of this legume has already been reported¹. The present communication deals with the fatty acid constituents of the seeds oil.

Fatty Acid Composition of *Cicer soongaricum* Steph. Seed Oil

S. K. KATIYAR* and A. K. BHATIA

Regional Research Laboratory, Jammu Tawi-180 001

Manuscript received 16 April 1985, revised 6 December 1985,
accepted 17 February 1986

CICER soongaricum Steph. (fam.: Leguminosae; local name *Sarri*) grows wild at an altitude of 3,000-5,000-m MSL in the Ladakh area of Jammu

Experimental

The seeds of *C. soongaricum* were collected during ethnobiological survey from South Pullu area (near Khardung La Pass, altitude 5 000 m MSL). The healthy and mature seeds were dried and ground upto 100-120 mesh.

The oil was solvent extracted using petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and purified by the method of Folch *et al.*². Methyl esters of the fatty acids were obtained by saponification of the oil, removal of

Fig. 1. GLC separation of fatty acids of *C. soongaricum* seed oil, I, II = unidentified peak.